

A STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS USING INSTRUCTIONAL AIDS AMONG B.ED TRAINEES IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Introduction:

The process of education is a lifelong process, from infancy to old age or from 'womb to grave'. Auro bindo defines Education as "Helping the growing soul to draw out that is in itself. Gandhi speaks of Education as, "By education, I mean an all-round drawing out of the best in the child and man-body, mind and spirit."

Educational Technology: Educational technology is a system in education in which machines, materials, media, men and methods are interrelated and work together for the fulfillment of specific educational objectives. Technology explosion has yielded several new machines, materials and media which have great potential for use in the educational enterprise. A Judicious use of these together with new functions and roles of educational personnel can bring about more efficient and effective teaching- learning. An adequate knowledge of theory and practices of educational technology and their proper use would enable the teacher to understand and effectively discharge his new roles in educational system in an age of "information explosion", "Knowledge explosion", "Population explosion", and "Expectation explosion".

Institutional Aids – Aids: Carter V. Good defines "Audio –visual aids are those aids which help in completing the triangular process of learning i.e., motivation, classification and stimulation. Edgar Dale states "Audio visual are those devices by the use of which communication of ideas between persons and groups in various teaching and training situations is helped. These are also termed as multi-sensory materials."

Need and Scope of the Study:

"Tell Me I Forgot. Show Me and I Remember. Involve Me and I Understand"

– Chinese Proverb

The use of instructional materials is a big help for the teacher trainees to facilitate the teaching-learning process. These Instructional Aids are important in motivating and arousing their student interest. Research and experiences have shown that instructional Aids increase and reinforce learning. Not only do they make the presentation more interesting but by engaging more than one of the senses they also facilitate listening and memorizing. While teaching, abstract concepts or unfamiliar subjects, visualization can be an essential tool of understanding. One reason B.Ed trainees may need to prepare instructional materials is used to develop a greater understanding of the content. It also allows material to be relevant to the specific needs of the students. The present study which aims at "a study on attitude towards using instructional Aids among B.Ed trainees in Coimbatore district" has been designed as a survey study.

Objectives of the Study:

General: To study on attitude towards using instructional Aids among B.Ed trainees in Coimbatore district.

Specific:

- ✓ To measure the degree of attitude towards using instructional Aids among B.Ed trainees.
- ✓ To find out the attitude of B.Ed trainees using instructional Aids in terms of gender.
- ✓ To find out the attitude of B.Ed using instructional Aids in terms of educational qualification.
- ✓ To the find out the attitude of B.Ed trainees using instructional Aids in terms of group of subjects.
- ✓ To the find out the attitude of B.Ed trainees using instructional Aids in terms of locality.

Research Questions:

- ✓ Is there any significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to gender?
- ✓ Is there any significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to Educational Qualification?
- ✓ Is there any significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to the group of their subject?
- ✓ Is there any significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to the group of their locality?

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There will be significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to gender.

- ✓ There will be significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to Educational Qualification.
- ✓ There will be significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to the group of their subject.
- ✓ There will be significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to the group of their locality.

Review:

Chukrar, David Andew (1992) studied the effect of students produced interactive multimedia modules on student learning. This study designed to measure effectiveness and feasibility of student’s production on interactive multimedia was conducted with seventy high school students in an environmental science course. The study revealed that students with little computer experience and no hyper condition experience produced interactive multimedia in a high school setting.

Golam, T. P. (2007) made the study with three objectives (1) To create awareness among teachers and head masters of secondary colleges about the importance of audio – visual aids. The tools of investigations were questionnaires to colleges head masters and teachers to assess to availability and use of Institutional Aidsaid in colleges, interviews to supplement the information available though questionnaires and visit and observations.

Study of the Study:

Population and Sample:

Population: The study will confined of B.Ed trainees of Coimbatore district.

Sample: Sample of 300 B.Ed trainees will be selected randomly from the different colleges in Coimbatore district.

Sample Technique: For this study the investigator will adopt the simple random sampling.

Variables:

Institutional Variables: Location (Rural/ Urban)

Student’s Variables:

- Gender (Male / Female)
- Educational Qualification (UG / PG)
- Group (Arts / Science)

Research Tools: In this investigation, the data will be collected using a questionnaire. The questionnaire was adopted simply it was TIAAS. TIAAS – Teachers Instructional Aids Attitude Scale – adopted by the investigator from R. Ambikadevi (2008-09). The scale covers all relevant aspects of instructional Aids. It had 30 items.

TIAAS: Teachers Instructional Aids Attitude Scale covers all the relevant aspects of Instructional Technology. It have 30 items. The TIAAS is used to seek B.Ed trainee attitude about Instructional Technology and integrating Instructional technology into the teaching learning process.

Scoring key for testing the attitude of B.Ed trainee towards using instructional technology:

Comparison Between Mean Score of B.Ed Trainees in Attitude of Using Instructional Aids With Respect to Gender:

H01: There will be significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to gender.

H11: There is no significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to gender.

Paired Samples Statistics:

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	T	Sig
Pair 1	Gender	1.70	300	.460	14.294	0.000
	Mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids	1.3199	300	.11791		

Interpretation: The above table shows about the comparison of mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional aids with respect to gender were the level of significance is at 0.000 with t value at 14.294 which is lesser than 0.05. Hence H11 alternative hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to gender.

Findings and Suggestions:

- ✓ Most of the respondents are female in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are doing their PG in our survey.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are from science group.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are from urban area.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the institutional aids help them to teach successfully.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the Instructional Aids help the learner to learn in a better way

- ✓ Most of the respondents said they have Instructional Aids based upon hardware approach.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the institutional aids are helping to motivate the learners.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents said the institutional aids are handy.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the instructional Aids helping the learner to become imaginative and creative
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the institutional aids are economical.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents the teaching learning process is not effective by using Instructional Aids.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are aware of the various type of Instructional Aids in teaching.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said they need explanation instructional Aids.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents said there is a chance of improving the child's understanding through Instructional Aids.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the institutional aids provoke additional mental ability.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the institutional aids provoke additional mental ability.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said they give importance to the individual instruction through Instructional Aids.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the teacher should have knowledge towards when to use the Instructional Aids.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the instructional aid makes the learners to modify their behaviour.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents said the complicated data given as simplified can be viewed through instructional Aids
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the institutional aids are entertaining the children.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said technical knowledge is required to operate through Instructional Aids.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the institutional aids needs many tools.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the Instructional Aids makes the teaching-learning process meaningful for the teacher
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the institutional aids controls the individual difference.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents said the institutional aids solves each and every problem in education
- ✓ Most of the respondents said the interaction between teacher and pupil is not must in teaching while using Instructional Aids.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said that Instructional Aids aims to improve the individual's learning mastery and competence.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that a teacher cannot create effective environment by using Instructional Aids
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents said the institutional aids can be used in a right way.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents said there is a need of ample
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents agree that instructional Aids are employed to improve the delivery of instruction.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said use of Instructional Aids is an art.

T-Test:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to educational qualification.
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to group of their subject.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the mean score of B.Ed trainees in attitude of using instructional Aids with respect to locality.

Conclusion:

- ✓ Education is very vital, deprived of education no can lead a good life. Teaching and learning are the important element in education. The teacher use different approaches and substantial to teach their students and their active learning
- ✓ In this study, the attitude towards using Instructional Aids among B.Ed trainee in Coimbatore district will be studied depend the variables location, gender, group and Educational qualification.
- ✓ The investigator reviewed the studies of Instructional Aids, which would move towards a right way. Methodology, tool developed for the data collection which will be followed in this study was explained

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